

Impact of Custom Duty and Rahdari Tax on Trade during the Mughal Period

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In the Mughal period, in addition to land revenue, more taxes were imposed, mainly on internal and external trade. Rahdari tax and Custom Duty were the chief among them. In addition to all this, the state used to get gifts from various quarters, huge amount of money in the war and tributes. All the items sold in the market were subject to some kind of tax. Taxes were levied on all types of items like clothes, leather, food grains, cattle etc. Every time a trader sold an item, he had to pay some tax. The description of the travellers of that time shows that these taxes were very harsh. Peter Mundy (1632) complains that “the governor at Patna was harsh in realizing taxes, and even women bringing milk for sale were not exempted”.¹ Writing in Aurangzeb’s reign, Shihabuddin Talish says that “every trader-from the rose-vendor down to clay-vendor, from the weaver of fine linen to that of coarse cloth had to pay tax”.²

Customs and rahdari tax were important but they were not the major sources of revenue of the empire. Nevertheless, the Mughals had taken good steps for the development of trade. Arif Qandahari says that, “In the early years of Akbar’s reign traders from many parts of the world engaged in trade with India without any complexity. The roads were safe, travel relatively easy, while tamgha (stamp tax for import), baj (toll levied by the road patrol), rahdari, Peshkash, were remitted: no taxes were realised from merchants”.³

Sher Shah imposed custom tax in Garhi (Sikrigali) during his reign and when the goods came through Khorasan, he taxed on his border. A second duty was levied at the place of sale. Sher Shah added to his officers that no custom tax should be levied on road, villages and hawkers.⁴ Even Babur, before battle of Khanwa in 1527, issued a farman to all his subjects that “We exempt (you) from all dues and octroi and tithe on corn and from all illegal imposts, so that no one trader or other may be hampered in his comings and goings, but all may move unmolested and free from interference”.⁵

Land revenue was the main tax in Mughal India but custom duty was also a major tax resource. Emperor used to determine import and export tax and the right to collect them was given to the governor or any other authority. Rates were not very high. In Surat in 1609, money (a term which include gold and silver whether coined or not) was levied at 2%, provisions for tax at 3% and goods for tax at 2½%.⁶

In the 17th century trade at the port clearly reveals three main things. The first of these three things was the delay in clearing of goods, second overvaluation and third compulsory sales. The British traders used to tell the reason of such delay to the “innate accustomed villainy” of the officials who, they added, “will do nothing without bribes, which however extorted, is made a continual custom, enforced as duty”; from this we can conclude that due to such charges, there was an increase in the sanctioned schedule of duties.⁷ According to Thevenot, “It was no small fortune for me to be so soon dispatched; for Men may wait sometimes a Month before they can get out their Baggage and especially they who have Merchants-goods, for which at that Custom-house they pay Four in the Hundred, if they be Christians, and Five in the Hundred if they be Banians”.⁸

Due to the increase in cheating and smuggling by foreign travellers, the checking of imported goods and consequently the delay became necessary. Sometimes the methods used by Smuggler were also very genius. During one such attempt, a captain was arrested with gold but was released due to giving 10% instead of 5%.⁹

The situation of overvaluation was more serious. Schedule was determined by price, but, while the rate dictated higher authority, the determination of the value of the commodity was left to the discretion of the officers. When they wanted to double their demand, they also doubled the value of the consignment undergoing custom. Apart from overvaluation and Delay, Surat officials also profited from forced dealing of goods coming to the custom house. They could reject the supply of goods for a long time. Traders complained that their goods were taken up and paid for at an insufficient rate.¹⁰ According to Mandelslo, “the governor and the custom officials both forced the merchants to part with at the price they thought fit to offer, those goods and commodities, which the merchants had brought for their own private use”.¹¹ In 1615, the British merchants complained that their goods were taken by the governor and the customer. Whereas it was either not paid at all or paid at an insufficient rate. After 35 years, their successors reported that goods were denied clearance for 2 years because they refused to accept the unsatisfactory price offered by the buyer. If we count bribes, forced sales and overvaluation, then it seems that the schedule of duty was of no importance in comparison to this demand.¹²

Under Akbar the custom duties did not exceed two and a half percent, as Abul Fazl stated that “the State takes certain taxes in harbour places but they never exceed two and a half percent which is so little compared with the taxes formerly levied, that merchants look upon harbour taxes as totally remitted and again he stated that the rule is that one-half or one-third of the tolls thus collected go to the State (the other half goes to the boatmen) and Merchants are therefore well treated, and the articles of foreign Countries are imported in large quantities”.¹³ In Tuzuk-i-Jahangiri, Jahangir says that “In the time of the Sultans of Gujarat customs of this port (Cambay) came to a large sum. Now in my reign it is ordered that they should not take more than one in forty (2.5%)”.¹⁴ William Finch, who arrived at Surat in 1608, found that the customs amounted to “two and half for goods, three for victuals, and two for money”.¹⁵

But subsequent statements by European travellers suggest that custom charges were increased to 3.5% in later years. Dutch Factor, Pelsaert, visiting India during the later years of Jahangir, says that “Custom duties are here three and an half percent on all imports and exports and two percent on money, either gold or silver”.¹⁶ According to Mandelso (in 1638), “the duty was three and a half percent ad-valorem on all commodities, except on gold and silver, whether in coins or in bars, which paid two Percent only”.¹⁷ According to English traveller John Ovington who came to India in 1689, “The custom paid for their goods by the Europeans is three percent, both out and in and they are privileged to lay their Goods in their Houses which they vent here, without being constrained to bring them to the Custom- House. The goods of all other Merchants are examined, and the Customs stated, which are 5 percent, that is 2 percent more than what is required from the European”.¹⁸ Tavernier also says that, “Private individuals pay as much as 4 and 5 percent duty on all their goods, but as for the English and the Dutch Companies, they pay less”.¹⁹ According to Tavernier, there was no benefit from this privilege. As he states: “I believe that, taking into account what it costs them in deputations and presents, which they are obliged to make every year at court, the goods cost them nearly the same as they do private persons”.²⁰

There was not much change in custom duty even during the reign of Shah Jahan and Aurangzeb. It was only up to 5% maximum. Shuja, the governor of Bengal, issued a farman to trade the Dutch without any hindrance and imposed only 5% duty on imports and exports. On 25 June 1667, Aurangzeb issued a farman to reduce the custom duty paid by English traders in Surat to only 2%.²¹

Rahdari was a minor charge, the proceeds of which paid for guarding the roads. Rahdars were sometimes appointed by kotwals, rarely on the emperor's order or by the zamidars. When a zamidari was awarded, among the holder's responsibilities was the protection of those using the roads and highways. To discharge this obligation he appointed

rahdars to guard travellers within his jurisdiction and in return he was entitled to ask rahdari from them.²² Rahdari was generally levied in proportion to the number of carts, bullocks, or persons in party. In the Deccan, for example during the reign of Shahjahan the tolls on bundles of cloth, when brought to the government warehouse by merchants, was one and half rupees plus three tankas per ox-load. When the cloth was removed for sale, the levy was three rupees plus three tankas per ox-load.²³ Pelsaert says, "Tolls at Broach in Western India were levied on goods whether they were brought into the towns for consumptions or merely transit. The rate was 1¼ percent calculated for all goods on the valuation of the qazi, or lawyer of the town".²⁴

Peter Mundy at Barnoli, 13 kos from Surat, was asked to pay Rs.20 as Jagat(toll or duty on good) for two carts, but after some argument he was allowed to pass, after paying only one shilling.²⁵ On the same journey, on the road between Bichola and Ichawara at a place called, by him Standeene Mundy paid Raya(Raja)of the place 3 rupees for 3 camels lading, the camel ½ rupee each and 2 pice a man.²⁶

On caravan routes there were chawkis where rahdari was levied. In Jahangir's time, on the Surat-Burhanpur road a caravan paid tolls at least in Baroda, Broach, Ankleshwar, Khirka, Varias and Dhaita.²⁷ Toll chawkis were maintained on rivers as well as on land. They were difficult to dodge. In Bengal there were many chawkis, as well as heavy traffic, which together caused considerable delays.²⁸

The duties on internal transit stand in a different position, because they were collected from English and Dutch, whose experience may be accepted as evidence of the ordinary working of system. Rahdari tax was a topic often used in commercial reports, on which there was always a deadlock. This tax was a hindrance in trade for foreigners who wanted to avoid it. Even for Indian traders it was mandatory to pay this tax. In the beginning of 1615, the British used to complain that they had to pay three separate taxes to bring goods from Ahmedabad to Surat for export. After some years, they were also taxed on the route to Burhanpur and Surat. An agreement was reached in Surat in 1624, which was also confirmed by Jahangir's farman that no land custom tax will be collected, yet this tax collected. The Dutch had a similar experience.²⁹ Khafi Khan says that "The Rahdari is a most vexatious impost and oppressive to travellers, but a large sum is raised by it. In most parts of the Imperial territories the faujdars and jagirdars, by force and tyranny, now exact more than ever from the traders and poor and necessitous travellers. The zamindars also, seeing that no inquiries are made, extort more on roads within their boundaries than is collected on roads under royal officers".³⁰

Jahangir, at the very inception of his regime, issued an ordinance "forbidding the levy of cesses under the names of tamgha and mirbahari (river tolls) and other burdens which the jagirdars had imposed for their own profit".³¹ Saqi Must'aid Khan of Aurangzeb's reign says that the Emperor "according to his usual generosity the collection of road-tolls (*rahdari*) on the transit of grains and other articles was abolished forever".³²

Thus, from these experiences, it is found that even after the emperor granted exemption from tax, these taxes had to be paid. But this exemption was not available to Hindu chiefs or kings whose territories came under the emperor's kingdom.³³ This system was not as rigorous under the Mughal Empire as it was outside the empire. Thevenot experienced this change when he entered the kingdom of Golconda and had to go through 16 taxing posts in 23 league journey.³⁴

In fact, the Mughals had no specific knowledge about the principle of taxation. Whenever they were happy, they used to give exemption from many taxes and when there was shortage of money, he used to tax many. He never considered how to apply taxation. Whenever any farman of tax exemption was issued, it was actually applied near the capital. In distant areas it was still collected by the Mughal officers. The Mughal history of taxation is full of Confusions. The situation was made worse by incorrect taxation. Many types of tax, unending greed of officials, complexity of tax, uncertainty of tax, repeated taxation by powerful person; all these were not beneficial for trade. Although the weight of taxation was less, but due to the

bribe given to various local and provincial authorities, it had more impact on the consumer. The inland transit duties were many and vexatious. Custom officers and collectors continued to collect transit duty. Foreign merchants somehow escaped paying taxes but native traders had to pay customs and transit duty. Foreign merchants had to pay expensive gifts to king, which equalized the benefit of tax exemption. When the provincial or local authorities required revenue, they could levy supplementary duty or tax. In the 17th century, the imposition of local tax for local needs had become a tradition, which Aurangzeb also tried to eliminate.

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